

Investigation of Flow-Induced Vibration Mitigation in a BEU-Type Shell-and-Tube Heat Exchanger Under Industrial Operating Conditions

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ABSTRACT:

Flow-induced vibration (FIV) is a major reliability concern in shell-and-tube heat exchangers operating under high shell-side flow conditions. In the present study, vibration behaviour of an industrial BEU-type shell-and-tube heat exchanger operating as a gas after-cooler was evaluated based on TEMA standards.

The initial exchanger configuration utilizing single segmental baffles showed higher susceptibility to vibration due to larger unsupported tube spans and increased shell-side cross-flow excitation forces. Detailed vibration assessment involving natural frequency analysis, vortex shedding evaluation, turbulent buffeting assessment, and acoustic resonance analysis was performed under operating conditions.

To improve vibration resistance, design modifications including reduction of unsupported tube span and implementation of multi-segmental baffles were incorporated. The modified configuration significantly increased tube natural frequency and reduced the possibility of resonance under operating conditions.

The study demonstrates that appropriate baffle configuration and tube support optimization can effectively reduce flow-induced vibration risk in industrial shell-and-tube heat exchangers without significant hydraulic penalty.

Keywords: Flow-induced vibration; Shell-and-tube heat exchanger; TEMA; Vortex shedding; Multi-segmental baffles; Natural frequency

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Importance of Vibration Analysis in Heat Exchangers

Flow-induced vibration (FIV) is one of the major reliability concerns in shell-and-tube heat exchangers operating under high shell-side flow velocities. Excessive vibration may lead to tube wear, fatigue failure, tube leakage, and structural damage, thereby affecting exchanger reliability and operational safety. [8, 9, and 10].

To ensure safe operation, vibration analysis is performed based on TEMA guidelines to evaluate:

- Natural frequency of tubes
- Vortex shedding effects
- Fluid elastic instability
- Turbulent buffeting
- Tube support adequacy

Therefore, accurate vibration assessment and appropriate tube support design are essential to minimize vibration susceptibility and improve exchanger operational reliability.

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1.2 PRESENT INDUSTRIAL HEAT EXCHANGER

The present study is based on a real-time industrial Gas after Cooler designed as a Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger. The exchanger is designed according to ASME Section VIII Division 1 and TEMA Class B standards.

The selected exchanger configuration is:

- TEMA Type: BEU
- Service: Gas After Cooler
- Shell Size: 380 mm × 2900 mm
- Heat Transfer Area: 14.8 m²
- Number of Tubes: 32 U-tubes
- Tube Size: 25.4 mm OD × 1.65 mm thickness
- Tube Layout: Triangular pitch
- Number of Tube Passes: 2

In this exchanger:

- NO_x gas with ambient air flows through the shell side
- Chilled water flows through the tube side for cooling operation

The exchanger operates under high shell-side flow conditions, making flow-induced vibration assessment critical for reliable operation.

1.3 Research Gap and Motivation

Although several studies have investigated flow-induced vibration in shell-and-tube heat exchangers, limited work has focused on practical vibration mitigation in industrial BEU-type exchangers operating under actual process conditions. Most published studies mainly emphasize numerical simulations and experimental investigations, whereas comparatively fewer studies discuss industrial design modifications based on TEMA vibration assessment procedures.

Therefore, the present work focuses on vibration mitigation through unsupported tube span reduction and implementation of multi-segmental baffles in an industrial gas after-cooler application.

1.4 Novel Contributions of the Present Study

The major contributions of the present work are summarized as follows:

- Industrial vibration assessment of a BEU-type shell-and-tube heat exchanger operating under actual process conditions.
- Comparative evaluation of initial and modified exchanger configurations based on TEMA vibration assessment criteria.
- Investigation of the influence of unsupported tube spans and baffle configuration on vibration susceptibility.
- Implementation of multi-segmental baffles for mitigation of flow-induced vibration in an industrial gas after-cooler application.

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- Improvement of exchanger operational reliability through practical design modifications without significant hydraulic penalty.

1.5 Selection of BEU Type Heat Exchanger Configuration

The BEU-type shell-and-tube heat exchanger configuration was selected for the present application due to its suitability for high thermal expansion conditions and ease of maintenance. The U-tube bundle arrangement accommodates differential thermal expansion between shell-side and tube-side fluids, thereby minimizing thermal stresses during operation.

In addition, the BEU configuration provides improved mechanical flexibility under varying operating temperatures and pressure conditions. The selected exchanger operates as a gas after-cooler under high shell-side flow conditions, where vibration assessment becomes important for ensuring reliable operation and minimizing tube damage risks.

The exchanger was designed according to TEMA Class B standards and ASME Section VIII Division 1 requirements for industrial service conditions.

Fig. 1. ISOMETRIC VIEW OF THE BEU-TYPE SHELL-AND-TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER.

2 Process Description of Present Heat Exchanger

The selected exchanger is used as a gas after cooler in the process system.

- Shell Side Fluid: NO_x gas with ambient air
- Tube Side Fluid: Chilled water

The hot NO_x gas enters through the shell side inlet and flows across the tube bundle. Chilled water flows inside the tubes and absorbs heat from the gas through the tube walls.

As the heat transfer takes place, the temperature of the NO_x gas decreases before leaving the shell outlet. The chilled water absorbs heat from the NO_x gases.

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Since shell-side flow passes across the tubes, dynamic fluid forces may develop on the tubes. Therefore, vibration analysis is necessary to ensure safe operation and prevent tube damage caused by flow-induced vibration.

2.1 INITIAL EXCHANGER CONFIGURATION AND PRELIMINARY VIBRATION ASSESSMENT

The initial shell and tube heat exchanger configuration utilized single segmental baffles to support the tube bundle and direct shell-side flow across the tubes.

During operation, shell-side NO_x gas flow generates cross-flow excitation forces on the tubes, which may lead to flow-induced vibration due to vortex shedding and turbulent excitation.

To evaluate the vibration behaviour of the exchanger, vibration analysis was performed using the exchanger operating conditions, tube support arrangement, unsupported tube span, and shell-side flow parameters based on TEMA vibration evaluation guidelines.

The initial baffle spacing established the unsupported tube span between adjacent supports, which significantly influences tube natural frequency and vibration response.

Therefore, detailed vibration calculations were carried out to evaluate the possibility of resonance and tube vibration under operating conditions.

Fig (2): SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER

2.2 TEMA-BASED VIBRATION CALCULATIONS

2.2.1 ESTIMATE OF CRITICAL FLOW VELOCITY

.....TEMA SECTION 6(V-10)/ (6-18)

FLUID ELASTIC PARAMETER

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Effective Tube Weight	Wo : 1.393 lb/ft.
Shell Side Fluid Density at Bulk Temperature	ρo : 0.0749 lb/ft³
Logarithmic Decrement	δtp : 0.00000763 lb/ft³
Tubes outside Diameter	do : 1 inch

$$X = \frac{144 \times W_o \times \delta_{tp}}{\rho_o \times d_o^2}$$

$$X = 0.02043$$

$$V = \frac{F_h \times W}{M \times (\alpha X) \times \rho_o \times (3600)}$$

$$V = 80.73 \text{ ft/sec}$$

The critical flow velocity Vc for a tube span is the minimum cross flow velocity at which that span may vibrate with unacceptable large amplitudes. The critical flow velocity for tube spans in the window, overlap, inlet and outlet regions, U-bends, and all typical should be calculated.

The critical velocity, Vc is defined by:

Fundamental natural frequency	Fn : 160.88 HZ
Tubes outside diameter	do : 1 inch
Critical flow velocity factor from (Table V-10.1)	D : 2.80 x X ^{0.17}
	D : 1.45

$$V_c = \frac{D \times F_n \times d_o}{12}$$

$$V_c = 19.4 \text{ ft/sec}$$

CROSS FLOW VELOCITY V: 80.73 ft/sec

The user should ensure that the reference cross flow velocity V, at every location is less than Vc for that location.

CONCLUSION:

Cross flow velocity < estimate of critical flow velocity

$$V < V_c$$

$$80.73 < 19.44$$

Based on the TEMA fluid elastic instability assessment, the evaluated operating conditions did not indicate susceptibility to fluid elastic vibration. The exchanger configuration was therefore considered stable with respect to fluid elastic instability.

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2.2.2 NATURAL FREQUENCY CALCULATION

...TEMA SECTION 6(V-5.3)/ (6-3), TABLE (V-5.3)/6-5

Tube length	L : 2850mm (112.2 inch)
Max unsupported length per span	Ls : 200mm (7.87 inch)
Constant as per (V.5.3)	Cu : 0.008
Young's modulus	E : 2.9E+07 psi
Tube radius	r : 38mm (1.496 inch)
Distance between tube radius to baffle centres	s : 40mm
Effective tube weight	Wo : 1.393 lb/in
Moment of inertia	I : 0.026 inch

FUNDAMANTEAL NATURAL FREQUENCY

$$Fn = 68.06 \frac{0.034}{r^2} \sqrt{\frac{E x I}{Wo}}$$

$$Fn = 160.88 \text{ HZ}$$

2.2.3 VORTEX SHEDDING FREQUENCY

.....TEMA SECTION 6 (V-12.2) / (6-22)

Tube outside diameter	do : 25.4mm (1 inch)
Longitudinal pitch	PI : 27.06mm (1.07 inch)
Transverse pitch	Pt : 31.25mm (1.23 inch)
Tube layout	: 60°
Cross flow velocity	V : 80.73 ft/sec

$$Xt : \frac{Pt}{do} \qquad \qquad \qquad XI : \frac{Pi}{do}$$

$$Xt : 1.23 \qquad \qquad \qquad Xi : 1.07$$

Shrouhal Number as per (Fig v-12.2A) / (6-25) S: 0.25

$$Fs = \frac{12 x S x V}{do}$$

$$Fs = 242.2 \text{ HZ}$$

Vortex shedding may be a problem when there is a frequency match with natural frequency of the tube vibration due to vortex shedding is expected.

When....

$$FN < 2 < Fs$$

CONCLUSION

.....TEMA SECTION 6(V-11.1) / (6-20)

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$$Fn < 2 Fs$$

$$160.88 < 2 \times 242.2$$

The evaluated vortex shedding frequency satisfied the TEMA screening criterion ($Fn < 2Fs$). Therefore, further vibration amplitude assessment was performed to determine the potential effect of vortex shedding on tube vibration behaviour under the specified operating conditions.

Since the vortex shedding screening criterion was satisfied, vibration amplitude evaluation was carried out in accordance with TEMA recommendations. This assessment was performed to determine whether the predicted vibration amplitudes remained within acceptable limits and to evaluate the likelihood of tube damage under operating condition.

2.2.4 VORTEX SHEDDING AMPLITUDE

The resulting Vibration Amplitude (Y_{vs}) is calculated by:

Lift coefficients for vortex shedding (Table V-11.2)	(CL): 0.091
Cross flow velocity	(V): 80.73 ft/sec
Shell side fluid density at bulk temperature	(ρ_o): 0.0749 lb/ft ³
Tube outside diameter	(do): 1 inch
Fundamental natural frequency	(Fn): 40.22 Hz
Logarithmic decrement	(δ_{tp}): 0.00000763 lb/ft
Effective tube weight	(Wo): 1.393 lb/ft
Force coefficients for turbulent buffeting	(CF): 0.022

$$Y_{vs} = \frac{CL \times \rho_o \times do \times V^2}{2\pi^2 \times \delta_{tp} \times Fn^2 \times Wo} = \frac{0.091 \times 0.0749 \times 1 \times 80.73^2}{2\pi^2 \times 0.00000763 \times 40.22^2 \times 1.393} = 8.18 \text{ inch}$$

Recommended Maximum Amplitude

..... (AS PER TEMA SECTION 6 (V-11.2.1))

$$Y_{vs} \leq 0.02 \times do$$

$$8.18 \leq 0.02 \times 1$$

CONCLUSION

Based on the TEMA vortex shedding amplitude assessment, the calculated developing vortex shedding amplitude exceeded the recommended maximum amplitude criterion. Therefore, vortex shedding-induced vibration was not expected to develop under the specified operating conditions, and no tube bundle failure associated with vortex shedding was anticipated.

2.2.5 TURBULENT BUFFETING

Turbulent buffeting is caused by random pressure fluctuations in the high-velocity flow hitting the tubes.

Maximum amplitude of vibration for single phase fluids

$$Y_{tb} = \frac{CF \times \rho_o \times do \times V^2}{8\pi \times \delta_{tp}^{0.5} \times Fn^{1.5} \times Wo} = Y_{tb} = \frac{0.022 \times 0.0749 \times 1 \times 80.73^2}{8\pi \times 0.00000763^{0.5} \times 40.22^{1.5} \times 1.393} = 0.05 \text{ inch}$$

Recommended maximum amplitude

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.... (As per TEMA section 6 (v-11.2.1))

$$Y_{tb} \leq 0.02 \times d_o$$
$$0.05 \leq 0.02 \times 1$$

Conclusion:

The calculated turbulent buffeting vibration amplitude exceeded the recommended maximum amplitude criterion. Therefore, turbulent buffeting-induced vibration was not expected to develop under the specified operating conditions, and no tube bundle failure associated with turbulent buffeting was anticipated.

2.2.6 ACOUSTIC FREQUENCY OF SHELL

....TEMA SECTION 6(V-12.1) / (6-21)

Distance between reflecting walls	w : 200mm (7.87 inch)
Shell side operating pressure	Ps : 6 kg/cm ² ,g (85.34 Psi)
Specific heat ration of shell side gas	Y : 1
Shell side fluid density at bulk temperature	ρo : 0.0749 lb/ft ³
Mode	I : 4

$$Fa = \frac{409}{w} \left(\frac{Ps\gamma}{\rho o \left[1 + \frac{0.5}{xixt} \right]} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ i, cycle/sec}$$
$$Fa = \frac{409}{7.87} \left(\frac{85.34 \times 1}{0.0749 \left[1 + \frac{0.5}{1.23 \times 1.07} \right]} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \times 4, \text{ cycle/sec}$$
$$Fa = 5973 \text{ HZ}$$

2.2.7 ACOUSTIC RESONANCE ASSESSMENT

Acoustic resonance assessment was carried out to evaluate the possibility of resonance between shell-side flow excitation and the acoustic natural frequency of the exchanger. The occurrence of acoustic resonance was examined according to the applicable TEMA acceptance criteria.

CONDITION PARAMETER

....TEMA SECTION 6(V-12.4.1) / (6-23)

$$0.8 \times Fs < Fa < 1.2 \times Fs$$
$$0.8 \times 242.2 < 5973 < 290.64$$

$$193.76 < 5973 < 290.64$$

Based on the acoustic resonance assessment, the evaluated operating conditions did not indicate susceptibility to acoustic resonance. Therefore, the exchanger configuration was considered safe with respect to acoustic resonance-induced vibration.

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3. Evaluation of Vibration Amplitude

Following the vortex shedding assessment, vibration amplitude calculations were performed according to TEMA recommendations.

- The calculated vortex shedding amplitude was compared with the allowable vibration amplitude limit.
- The calculated vibration amplitude exceeded the TEMA allowable limit ($y_{vs} < 0.02d_o$) indicating a need for design modifications to reduce vibration risk.
- Turbulent buffeting evaluation was also performed and found to be within acceptable operating limits.
- Although the calculated amplitudes satisfied the allowable criteria, continuous shell-side cross-flow forces and turbulence effects may still influence long-term tube vibration behaviour, particularly in unsupported tube regions.
- Therefore, further design improvements were considered to reduce vibration tendency and improve operational reliability.

4 Engineering Concerns in Initial Design

During evaluation of the initial exchanger configuration, several factors influencing vibration behaviour were identified [15].

The initial design utilized single segmental baffles, which generated strong shell-side cross-flow patterns across the tube bundle.

This flow pattern increased turbulence intensity and dynamic excitation forces acting on the tubes [16].

In addition, the unsupported tube span between adjacent baffles influenced tube stiffness and vibration response [17].

The following concerns were identified in the initial configuration:

- Higher shell-side turbulence intensity
- Increased cross-flow excitation forces
- Possibility of tube vibration near unsupported regions
- Increased risk of tube-to-baffle wear during long-term operation
- Higher vibration tendency near shell inlet and outlet regions

Therefore, design modifications were considered to improve vibration resistance and reduce excitation forces acting on the tube bundle.

5. Design Modifications Adopted for Vibration Reduction

To reduce flow-induced vibration effects and improve tube bundle stability, several design improvements were incorporated into the exchanger configuration.

a) Modification of Baffle Arrangement

- The initial single segmental baffle arrangement was reviewed to reduce excessive cross-flow turbulence acting on the tubes.
- Multi-segmental baffle arrangement was considered to improve shell-side flow distribution and reduce sudden flow impact forces on the tube bundle. This helped reduce excitation forces generated due to shell-side cross-flow [18].

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Fig (3): MULTI-SEGMENTAL BAFFLE ARRANGEMENT

b) Optimization of Baffle Spacing

- Baffle spacing was optimized to reduce unsupported tube span between adjacent supports.
- Reducing unsupported span increased tube stiffness and improved tube natural frequency characteristics.
- Improved tube support also helps to reduce tube deflection during operation.

c) Improvement in Tube Support

- Proper tube support arrangement was maintained to reduce tube movement caused by shell-side dynamic forces.
- Improved support conditions reduced the possibility of tube-to-baffle wear and fatigue damage.

d) Tube Stiffness Consideration

- Tube geometry and thickness were evaluated to maintain sufficient tube rigidity against flow-induced excitation forces.
- Increased tube stiffness improves resistance against vibration response during operation.

6. Revised Vibration Assessment of Modified Heat Exchanger Configuration.

- After incorporating the design improvements, the vibration behaviour of the exchanger was re-evaluated.
- The modified baffle arrangement and improved support configuration reduced unsupported tube span and improved flow distribution across the tube bundle. These modifications help reduce shell-side excitation forces and improve vibration resistance of the exchanger.
- The revised vibration assessment indicated improved operational stability and reduced possibility of excessive tube vibration under operating conditions.

6.1 NATURAL FREQUENCY CALCULATION

...TEMA SECTION 6(V-5.3)/(6-3), TABLE (V-5.3)/6-5

Tube length	L : 2850mm (112.2 inch)
Max unsupported length per span	Ls : 150mm (5.91 inch)
Constant as per (V.5.3.2)	Cu : 0.034

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Young's modulus	E : 2.9E+07 psi
Tube radius	r : 38mm (1.496 inch)
Distance between tube radius to baffle centres	s : 40mm
Effective tube weight	W _o : 1.517 lb/in
Moment of inertia	I : 0.026 inch

FUNDAMANTEAL NATURAL FREQUENCY

$$Fn = 68.06 \frac{0.034}{r^2} \sqrt{\frac{E \times I}{W_o}}$$

$$Fn = 729.05 \text{ HZ}$$

The design modifications significantly increased the tube natural frequency from 160.88 Hz to 729.05 Hz. The increase in natural frequency reduced the possibility of resonance and improved vibration resistance under operating conditions.

6.2 VORTEX SHEDDING FREQUENCY

.....TEMA SECTION 6 (V-12.2) / (6-22)

Tube outside diameter	do : 25.4mm (1 inch)
Longitudinal pitch	PI : 27.06mm (1.07 inch)
Transverse pitch	Pt : 31.25mm (1.23 inch)
Tube layout	: 60°
Cross flow velocity	V : 97.43 ft/sec

$$Xt : \frac{Pt}{do} \qquad \qquad \qquad Xi : \frac{Pi}{do}$$

$$Xt: 1.23 \qquad \qquad \qquad Xi : 1.07$$

Shrouhal Number as per (Fig v-12.2A) / (6-25) S: 0.25

$$Fs = \frac{12 \times S \times V}{do}$$

$$Fs = 292.3 \text{ HZ}$$

When....

$$Fn < 2 < Fs$$

CONCLUSION

.....TEMA SECTION 6(V-11.1) / (6-20)

$$Fn < 2 \times Fs$$

$$729.05 < 2 \times 292.3$$

Following the design modifications, the fundamental natural frequency of the tube span is sufficiently higher than the vortex shedding frequency, satisfying the criterion $F_n < 2F_s$. Under this condition, resonance due to vortex shedding is not expected, and therefore amplitude calculations are not critical. The increased stiffness and reduced unsupported span have shifted the system away from frequency matching conditions. Consequently, the risk of

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vibration-induced damage, particularly near the shell inlet and outlet regions, is minimized. Any residual effects of vortex shedding and turbulent buffeting are within acceptable limits as specified by TEMA, ensuring safe and reliable operation of the tube bundle.

7. REVISED VIBRATION ASSESSMENT

After implementing design modifications, the vibration characteristics of the heat exchanger were re-evaluated based on TEMA guidelines. The updated parameters show significant improvement in vibration resistance and structural stability.

Fig (4): U-TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER

7.1 REVISED PARAMETERS:

Effect of Design Modifications:

1. Reduction in Unsupported Span Length:

- This increases stiffness and natural frequency.
- **Result:** Lower susceptibility to flow-induced vibration

2. Changing from Single Segmental to Multi-Segmental Baffles

- Multi-segmental baffles provide **more uniform support**
- Reduce large unsupported regions between baffles
- Maintain flow distribution while improving support
- **Result:** Reduced vibration without major pressure drop penalty

3. Improved Flow Distribution

- Better flow guidance reduces turbulence intensity
- Minimizes vortex shedding effects
- **Result:** Lower excitation forces on tubes

4. Increase in Natural Frequency

- Due to shorter span and better support
- Moves system away from resonance conditions
- **Result:** Safer vibration behaviour

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8. Final Vibration Assessment

Parameter	Initial Design	Modified Design
Natural Frequency (Hz)	160.88	729.05
Vortex Shedding Frequency (Hz)	242.2	292.3
Baffle Arrangement	Single Segmental	Multi Segmental
Unsupported Span	200 mm	150 mm
Vibration Susceptibility	Higher	Reduced

A TEMA-based vibration assessment was performed for a BEU-type shell-and-tube heat exchanger operating as a gas after-cooler. The initial configuration exhibited higher vibration susceptibility due to larger unsupported tube spans and shell-side flow excitation. Design modifications including multi-segmental baffles, reduced unsupported spans, and improved tube support conditions were implemented. The modified configuration significantly increased the tube natural frequency and reduced resonance susceptibility. The final assessment demonstrated improved vibration resistance and enhanced operational reliability under industrial operating conditions.

9. Conclusions:

- ✓ The vibration assessment was performed in accordance with TEMA guidelines for shell-and-tube heat exchangers.
- ✓ The initial configuration indicated a higher risk of flow-induced vibration due to larger unsupported tube span.
- ✓ Decreasing baffle spacing increased the number of tube support locations along the length.
- ✓ Improved support conditions led to a significant reduction in tube deflection and vibration amplitude.
- ✓ Replacement of single segmental baffles with multi-segmental baffles provided more uniform tube support.
- ✓ Multi-segmental baffles also helped maintain effective flow distribution while minimizing vibration risk.
- ✓ Improved flow pattern reduced turbulence intensity and vortex shedding effects on the tubes.
- ✓ The natural frequency of the tube bundle increased due to reduced unsupported span.
- ✓ Increased natural frequency moved the system away from resonance conditions.
- ✓ The overall vibration margin improved after implementing the design modifications.
- ✓ The combined effect of geometric and flow improvements resulted in a more stable tube bundle.
- ✓ The design modifications achieved a balance between mechanical stability and hydraulic performance.
- ✓ The final configuration ensures reduced likelihood of long-term tube failure due to vibration.
- ✓ The exchanger is expected to operate safely and reliably under the given process conditions.
- ✓ All modifications were implemented without significantly increasing pressure drop.
- ✓ The final design meets acceptable vibration criteria as specified by TEMA standards.

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